

D6.2: Guide on Online Platform

Authors: O. Schreer (HHI), F. Mushtaq (UoL)

Editor: O. Schreer (HHI)

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Contributor(s):	M. Barngrover (XR4Europe)
Reviewer(s):	Marco Correa (LU), Rigmor Barras (USN)
Approved by	Rigmor Barras (USN)

ABSTRACT:	This document outlines the objectives, features, and capabilities of the Online Platform available to the public through the XR4Human website (https://xr4human.eu/experience). It also addresses the platform's maintenance, ongoing development, and planned activities beyond M24, leading to the project's completion.
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Consortium:

	ROLE	NAME	Short Name	Country
1.	Coordinator	UNIVERSITETET I SOROST-NORGE	USN	NO
2.	Partner	XR4EUROPE	XR4Europe	BE
3.	Partner	UNIVERSITETET I OSLO	UiO	NO
4.	Partner	ETHNICON METSOVION POLYTECHNION	NTUA	EL
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9.	Partner	FRAUNHOFER GESELLSCHAFT ZUR FORDERUNG DER ANGEWANDTEN FORSCHUNG EV	Fraunhofer	DE
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11.	Partner	STICHTING FONTYS	Fontys	NL
12.	AP	UNIVERSITY OF LEEDS	UNIVLEEDS	UK

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1 Introduction

This document outlines the objectives, features, and capabilities of the “Online Platform” available to the public through the XR4Human website (<https://xr4human.eu/experience>). It also addresses the platform’s maintenance, ongoing development, and planned activities beyond M24, leading to the project’s completion. During the preparation for the platform’s launch, the partners chose to name this resource the XR4HUMAN “Experience Library.” The reason for this change is that the term “online platform” (used in the Grant Agreement) may imply a tool for communication, whereas the current offering is more accurately described as a repository. Therefore, in this document, the term Experience Library (EL) will be used.

2 Objectives of the Experience Library

As outlined in the Grant Agreement, Task 6.3 (Launch and Management of an Online Platform) specifies that the consortium will manage a platform to host outputs from Task 6.2 and allow the community to demonstrate adherence to best practices by uploading their own experiences.

Following discussions during the most recent period, the partners concluded the following regarding the platform’s capabilities and offerings:

- The platform should function as an online repository, allowing the community to search for, access, and upload XR experiences.
- The platform should not host the XR applications themselves to avoid complications related to version control, storage space, and other logistical issues.
- The responsibility for maintaining and supporting the XR applications should remain with the institutions providing them, ensuring that they manage all aspects of installation and updates.
- The platform should provide clear contact information and links to the institutions’ servers to facilitate access to the XR applications.
- GDPR compliance must be maintained, with appropriate measures in place to protect users’ data during the exchange of information between the platform and the institutions.

Furthermore, it is essential to clearly state the differences and unique selling points of this Experience Library compared to other commercial and non-commercial repositories of XR experiences. Hence, the following Unique Selling Propositions (USPs) have been developed:

1. Curated Focus on Non-Commercial XR Applications

A dedicated platform that highlights non-commercial and experimental XR projects, providing developers with an alternative to more generic repositories like GitHub. Non-commercial means that the installation and use of the XR projects is free of charge without any costs.

2. Increased Discoverability for Developers and Their Work

Boost visibility of both individual XR developers and their projects, offering ethical branding opportunities that showcase commitment to responsible tech development.

3. Non-Commercial Demos of Commercial Projects

Developers can showcase demos of commercial XR projects or can share their projects after they no longer serve commercial purpose to increase the return on their investments.

4. Ethical Development and Brand Alignment

Developers can associate their work with ethical XR practices, enhancing their credibility and attracting consumers who prioritise ethical design and development.

5. EU Project Showcases

A space for EU-funded projects to submit demos, pilots, and MVPs, providing a valuable platform for sharing early-stage innovations with a broad audience.

6. Consumer Engagement in Ethics Research

Visitors can explore the intersection of ethics and XR technology, with curated experiences linking library projects to relevant discussions in the XR4HUMAN Forum.

7. Badge System for Ethical Recognition

Projects can earn an ethical development badge, which is represented by risk-of-harm descriptors through the forthcoming Code of Conduct. These descriptors will provide information that can help users to make informed discussions about whether they want to engage in the experience or not. It will provide developers with a marketing tool that highlights their commitment to responsible XR practices.

8. Opportunities for XR Content Creators of Tomorrow

Provides early-career developers and students with a unique opportunity to showcase their portfolios to an international audience. By participating in the repository, they can gain visibility and credibility and position themselves at the forefront of responsible XR practices.

3 Content curation

It is essential to define criteria and a workflow for the submission of XR experiences. The first and most important aspect is that the content created by application developers is for **non-commercial use** and demonstrates ethical/inclusive practices. Application developers can be companies, institutions, students, or independent persons.

Furthermore, it is also important to clearly explain the criteria of the evaluation procedure for inclusion of applications in the Experience Library. The criteria are listed below and will be available on the EL. Therefore, XR4Human installed an Advisory Board (AB), which will be periodically reviewing applications. The AB is composed of members of WP6, which are senior researchers or professors with plenty years of experience in XR. This means that applications are aggregated and reviewed in scheduled cycles. After the end of the project, the AB will be a group of experts from the XR community that are performing the review on a voluntary basis, and which are capable to test and run the different submissions during the review.

The submissions will undergo the following selection criteria:

1. Non-Commercial Demonstration

Submissions must be non-commercial in nature, at least in the form of the demo or application being made available free of charge without any costs. Commercial concepts are allowed, but the available version must remain non-commercial. There is no need to be released under an open licence.

2. Acknowledgment of Code of Conduct

Applicants must read and acknowledge the project's Code of Conduct, confirming their understanding via a check box.

3. Self-Assessment Submission

Developers are required to submit a self-assessment form that focuses on key ethical principles, including language support, accessibility, and data privacy. The assessment will be reviewed as part of the selection process. The self-assessment form is presented in Annex 2.

4. Acceptance of Ethical Evaluation

While not part of the selection criteria, developers must agree to have their project evaluated with respect to the forthcoming Code of Conduct and related risk-of-harm descriptors. The assessment will be initially carried out by the AB.

At the time of writing of this deliverable, the criteria above cannot be applied in total as the project has not yet finalized a publicly available Code of Conduct. As soon as the CoC will be available, all applicants of recently accepted XR experiences will be asked to acknowledge the Code of Conduct. Otherwise, the XR experience will be removed from the library.

The criteria will be outlined on the Experience Library to inform the applicants about. In terms of sustaining the platform after the end of XR4Human, we will transition from an XR4Human-led AB to a community-led review process.

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4 Features of the Experience Library

The Experience Library is part of the XR4Human web site and offers the following features:

1. An introductory page presents the objectives and the features of the Experience Library and allows users to search for XR applications on the EL based on a variety of tags (see Figure 1). This page also offers a User Guide, how to explore the EL and how to make submissions. Furthermore, a direct link to the submission form is available, which allows potential applicants to submit their XR project.
2. A filter is made available to search for distinct XR experiences. Filter parameters are for example the technology (AR, VR), the required hardware, the application domain and many more (see categories below).
3. The current available XR applications are displayed in separate boxes. If specific filter options have been selected, the related search results are presented (see Figure 2).
4. For each of the resulting XR applications, a more detailed page is available that gives the user all the necessary information including advice how to access and download the application (see Figure 3-5).
5. A submission form that offers XR developers and application providers to gather the required information that is necessary to publish their experience on the EL (see Annex 1).

The offering of the XR experiences to the public will be made available in the form of links that point either to other web sites or to cloud storage, from where the experience can be downloaded.

Figure 1 Main page of the Experience Library

Figure 2 Filters and list of available XR experiences on the main page.

Figure 3 Project description (1) with information about the submitter and a short text about the XR experience.

Figure 4 Project description (2) with teaser material and information how to access as well as technical information.

Project Details

Creators of this project:
University or Research Project

Date of completion:
12/01/2023

Acceptable conditions:
The app does not collect or share any personal information.
The app does not access the user's personal data stored on the device. The app does not access the user's location data.
The app does not access the user's IP address. The app does not collect data about the user's device.

Share to social

Go back to XR Experiences

Submit an XR Experience

Figure 5 Project description (3) additional information.

The experiences are tagged in order to allow easy search and sorting. The relevant tags are as follows:

- Technology: AR, MR, VR, 360 Video (3DoF), Generative Artificial Intelligence, Photogrammetry, Volumetric Recording, Digital Twinning, others
- Required hardware: Standalone VR Headset, PCVR Headset, MR-capable Headset, Mobile Device (Phone or Tablet / Android or iOS), Dome + Projector, others
- Domain: Industrial / Manufacturing, Medical / Healthcare, Cultural Heritage, Social Impact, Cinema / Media, Education, Documentary, Social, Gaming
- UX: Single-user, multi-user, both

All the offered XR experiences are stored in a light-weight content management system (CMS) that contains all the relevant information about the experience such as:

- Submitter (name, role institution/company, email)
- Short description
- Domain
- Teaser image or even video
- Required hardware and platform
- Language
- Technology
- UX (single / multi-user)
- Acceptable conditions for the download and use of the experience
- License or copyright status
- Contact details and download link
- Year of creation (and/or last update)

The information above must be provided by the submitting institution based on an online submission form. This form contains check boxes and fields for the requested information. The submission form is hosted on a QUALTRICS server at University of Leeds and fulfils GDPR requirements (https://leedspsychology.eu.qualtrics.com/jfe/form/SV_dokNC31E2kB1z6u) (see Annex 1 for details).

5 Institutional workflow

The submission and the inclusion of new experiences must be clearly defined in order to be compliant with GDPR and to guarantee transparency.

Any interested party can submit an XR experience via the given submission form. After submission, the information is forwarded to the AB that will also act as an ethics committee. The AB will test the download and installation procedure of the submission. After successful completion of the installation, the XR experience will be executed and evaluated against the ethical requirements by using the criteria defined in sec.3. After AB-internal discussion, a common agreement will be reached among the AB-members and the submission will be either accepted for publication on the EL or rejected.

The AB also continuously checks the status of already included XR experiences. If the XR experience is not any more accessible or any other issues such as commercialisation turned out, the XR experience will be removed from the EL.

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6 The official launch

On April 31st, 2024, the XR4Human Experience Library went online and can be accessed via the XR4Human web site at <https://xr4human.eu/experience/> . The launch was communicated via social media. In conjunction with this, members of WP6 organized a LinkedIn event on May 7th, 2024. In this online event, the project and the activities of WP6 were presented. After that, a more detailed walk-through the Experience Library demonstrated the features, the capabilities and how to contribute by using the submission form.

Figure 6 Participation at the online event on 7th May 2024

7 Future work

The presented first public version of the Experience Library will be further optimised and improved. Depending on the user feedback, we will modify the submission form, improve the project presentation on the platform or optimise the searchability.

To ensure the sustainability of the Experience Library and its long-term impact, we are actively seeking connections with other XR communities (e.g. Immersive Learning Research Network) and relevant stakeholders, including university graduate and postgraduate programs (having connected already with programmes represented by our consortium). The capabilities of the EL and the given opportunities to applicants are continuously communicated via social media. If any new submission is available on the EL, the XR4HUMAN project will communicate this via social media to the XR community.

By collaborating with academic institutions, we expect to be able to use the Experience Library as both an educational tool to disseminate the outcomes of XR4Human and a showcase for innovative projects that might otherwise lack visibility. This dual purpose will not only help raise awareness of XR4Human's contributions but also foster the growth of the Experience Library by encouraging new submissions from educational institutions and the XR developers of tomorrow. We will also leverage other work in WP6, particularly the survey and Delphi study, to establish best practices for XR experiences. The Delphi study aims to reach consensus on key aspects of XR design and user experience. From the areas where consensus is achieved, we will explore whether this can help guiding the development of the Code of Conduct and the definition of risk-of-harm descriptors. Those will then be used to classify applications based on their adherence to these best practices, offering users a clear indication of quality. For reference, a similar approach is used in the Open Science movement (see: <https://www.apa.org/pubs/journals/resources/open-science-badges>).

Finally, in collaboration with WP7, we will also implement a rating system for each accepted application. This will encourage user engagement by fostering discussions on the quality and effectiveness of the XR experiences. These discussions will take place in the forum under the category "Best Practices in XR Design," providing a valuable space for the community to share insights and improve the overall quality of experiences available in the library.

Annex 1: Submission Form

Important information about how we will handle your responses. All submissions are to be non-commercial projects free of charge and without any costs. All submissions are reviewed by an Advisory Board that evaluates projects along criteria established through the XR4HUMAN project's work. Acceptance for inclusion in the Experience Library is also determined by the appropriateness of the XR experience submitted. The applicant(s) must commit to hosting or be responsible for explaining and facilitating access to their XR experience. The Library does not host any experience files; it simply curates and evaluates accepted experiences for the benefit of the industry and the public. The Library will be maintained by XR4Europe beyond the project lifespan as part of its commitment to support the European XR community. Your submissions will be handled by the Centre for Immersive Technologies at the University of Leeds as part of the European Union's Horizon Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement no. 101070155 and the UKRI through the Horizon Europe Guarantee (#10039307).

What is the name of the XR experience that you are submitting?

Please provide your full name

Your role with regard to the project you are submitting,

Please describe the creator(s) of this project (tick all that apply)

- University or Research Project
- Student Project
- Private Company (i.e. Creative Studio or media agency)
- Consortium Project (i.e. EU-funded project)

Email Address

Provide a link to the XR experience or contact person from which your application's executable files can be obtained.

Please briefly describe your XR experience project (200 - 500 words), including your purpose for making and sharing it and provide any important details about how its production and stakeholders.

Please share a link to teaser images and/or videos of the experience so that they can be used on the website alongside your submission.

Please detail the license this experience is available under. If you are unclear on which is the right one for your experience, please take a look at this Creative Commons [webpage](http://https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/cclicenses/).

- CC BY (Creative Commons Attribution)
 - CC BY-SA (Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike)
 - CC BY-NC (Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial)
 - CC BY-NC-SA (Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
 - CC BY-ND (Creative Commons Attribution-NoDerivs)
 - CC BY-NC-ND (Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)
 - CC0 Public Domain Dedication (Creative Commons Zero)
 - Full copyright, but free of charge
 - Other _____
-

Please describe the acceptable conditions for use or exhibition of your experience.

When was the current version of the experience completed? Enter closest approximate date.

	Month	Year
Please Select:	▼ January ... December	▼ 1900 ... 2049

Do you have additional supplementary material to be provided to the platform? If yes, please share the link to where those materials can be accessed.

Please indicate which technologies are utilized in the experience? Tick all that apply.

- Augmented Reality
- Mixed Reality
- Virtual Reality
- 360 Video (3DoF)
- Generative Artificial Intelligence

- Photogrammetry
- Volumetric Recording
- Digital Twinning
- Other _____

Please indicate which hardware is required to experience or exhibit your project. You can enter text alongside your selection to specify the model. Tick all that apply.

- Standalone VR Headset (state model) _____
- PCVR Headset _____
- MR-capable Headset _____
- Mobile Device (Phone or Tablet / Android or iOS) _____
- Dome + Projector _____
- Other _____

Please indicate which operating system your experience is compatible with. Tick all that apply.

- Windows
- Mac
- Android
- iOS
- N/A
- Other _____

Please select the domain(s) or subject area(s) that best describe your experience. Tick all that apply.

- Industrial / Manufacturing
- Medical / Healthcare
- Cultural Heritage
- Social Impact
- Cinema / Media
- Education
- Documentary
- Social
- Gaming
- Other _____

Is your experience suited for a single-user or multiple users?

- Single User
- Multiple User
- Both are possible

Do you have any feedback, suggestions, or questions about this submission form or XR4HUMAN's Experience Library? If yes, please share those below:

Finally, please sign to confirm that you have the right to submit this XR experience for evaluation and inclusion in the XR4HUMAN Experience.

Thank you! We will be in touch as soon as the Review Panel have met and considered your submission. Clicking next will redirect you to the XR4Human Experience Library webpage.

End of Block: Thank You

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Annex 2: Self Assessment Form

XR4HUMAN Experience Library Self-Assessment Form

Thank you for submitting your XR project to the XR4HUMAN Experience Library. Please complete this self-assessment form to verify that your submission aligns with our ethical and technical standards.

1. Non-Commercial Focus

This section ensures that the project being submitted aligns with the requirement to be non-commercial in nature for the purpose of this repository.

- My project is submitted as a non-commercial demo or application.
- The commercial concept (if applicable) is not being monetised or sold through this submission.
- I confirm that my project does not contain any commercial advertising or promotional materials.

2. Code of Conduct & Interoperability Guide Acknowledgment *****To be confirmed once the Code of Conduct is revised, aligned with forthcoming work and published*****

This section confirms that you understand and adhere to the ethical and technical guidelines set forth by the platform.

- I have read and understood the XR4HUMAN Experience Library Code of Conduct.

3. Ethical and Inclusive Design

This section evaluates the inclusivity, accessibility, and ethical considerations of your project.

- My project supports accessibility features such as text-to-speech, adjustable fonts, or subtitles.
- My project includes multi-lingual support or provides language options for non-English speakers.
 - Please list supported languages: _____
- My project takes into account cultural sensitivities and avoids harmful stereotypes or biases.
- I have implemented privacy-by-design principles, ensuring that data collection is minimised and user privacy is respected.
 - The project includes clear consent mechanisms for any data collection.

4. User Safety and Well-Being

This section confirms that user safety and well-being are prioritized throughout the experience.

- My project has been developed with user safety in mind, minimising risks such as motion sickness, physical discomfort, or mental distress.
- I have considered the potential psychological impact of my project, ensuring that it does not promote harm or cause unnecessary stress or anxiety.
- Clear instructions and warnings are provided to users to ensure a safe and comfortable experience.

5. Data Privacy and Security

This section assesses how the project handles sensitive data and ensures user privacy.

- My project does not collect unnecessary personal data from users.
- Where personal data is collected, I have obtained consent or I have duly informed users of other legal bases for data processing in the context of my project.
- Where personal data is collected, I have implemented encryption and other security measures to protect user information.
- I provide users with clear information on how their personal data will be used, stored, and protected (e.g. privacy policy).
- I declare that my project is fully compliant with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

6. Environmental Sustainability

This section focuses on sustainability practices in the development of the XR project.

- I have considered the environmental impact of my project, minimising energy consumption where possible.
- My project is designed to be efficient in terms of hardware requirements, reducing unnecessary resource consumption.
- I have explored opportunities for extending the project's lifecycle, such as future-proofing updates or scalability.

7. Additional Information

Please provide any additional context or details that might help us better understand your project.

- My project supports additional XR hardware or platforms. (List any supported platforms: _____)
- I would like my project to be featured in discussions on specific ethical topics in XR technology. (List topics: _____)

8. Submission Checklist

Please ensure you have completed all required fields before submitting your project.

I declare that I own or have the right to use and publish this project in the Experience Library.

I have filled out this self-assessment form honestly and to the best of my knowledge.

I acknowledge that incomplete or inaccurate assessments may delay the review process or lead to the rejection of the submission.

I release the XR4Human initiative from any responsibility arising from the use and publication of my project in the Experience Library or from any inconsistencies or inaccuracies in my submission.

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